

The Effect of Added (C-16) α -Olefin Sulphonate on Micelle Concentration of Sodium Lauryl Sulphate

H. S. RANDHAWA*, ABHA NARRU and M. L. SOOD

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 16 November 1992, revised 11 October 1993, accepted 1 March 1994

The micellar behaviour of single surfactant system is well understood¹. Studies on micellar behaviour of binary surfactant systems have gained significant importance². Addition of minute quantities of one surfactant has significant influence on the micellar behaviour of another surfactant³. Such synergistic effects have been extensively exploited in industry⁴. Hence, it is thought worthwhile to investigate the micellar behaviour of a mixed surfactant system containing two anionic surfactants, namely, sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) and (C-16) α -olefin sulphonate (AOS). AOS, a fourth generation anionic surfactant, has recently become available in India on commercial scale. It has a wide range of applications and studies on the micellar behaviour of mixed surfactant system containing AOS are scanty⁵.

Results and Discussion

The c.m.c. values for the surfactants and the mixed surfactant systems were determined as the point of intersection of lines, i.e. from curve of physical property versus logarithm of molar concentration, extrapolating the measured properties of surfactant from above and below the regions in which a rapid change of slope is observed. The c.m.c. values obtained by three methods are recorded in Table 1. It is observed that c.m.c. of pure AOS is less than that of pure SLS. The low value of c.m.c. of AOS in comparison to that of SLS is expected from a longer hydrophobic chain length in the molecule¹. It is observed that for pure SLS, the c.m.c. obtained by spectral change method was lower than that obtained by the other two methods. This lowering in the c.m.c. may be attributed to the induced micelle formation caused by the presence of an anionic dye in the micellar system⁶.

TABLE 1—c.m.c. VALUES OF AQUEOUS SURFACTANT SOLUTIONS OF AOS AND SLS OBTAINED BY THREE DIFFERENT METHODS

Mole fraction of AOS in aqueous SLS	10 ³ c.m.c. (mol dm ⁻³)		
	Surface tension method	Viscometric method	Spectral method
0.00	7.94	8.41	6.20
0.10	6.31	6.16	5.80
0.20	5.62	5.88	5.60
0.30	5.62	5.62	5.20
0.40	5.49	5.49	5.10
0.50	5.43	5.49	5.00
0.60	5.37	5.43	4.90
0.70	5.30	5.18	4.70
0.80	5.24	5.12	4.60
0.90	5.24	5.01	4.40
1.00	5.01	4.67	4.30

Theoretically if there is no interaction between SLS and AOS and the mixed micelles are ideal, the c.m.c. values for the binary surfactant systems would fall on the line predicted from the relationship⁷,

$$\frac{1}{C_{12}^M} = \frac{\alpha}{C_1^M} + \frac{1-\alpha}{C_2^M} \quad (1)$$

where α is the mole fraction of AOS in the binary surfactant system, C_1^M , C_2^M and C_{12}^M are that for AOS, SLS and the mixed surfactant system respectively. The results reveal that the c.m.c. of binary system determined by various techniques fall below the theoretical values, indicating that this system exhibits considerable deviation from ideality.

Experimental

Commercial grade samples of AOS and SLS (Table 2) (Dharmasi Morarji Chemical Company)

were used as such. Their stock solutions (0.5 M each) were prepared in double-distilled water. These stock solutions were used to prepare the solutions of each of these surfactants and the binary mixed surfactant systems. The c.m.c. values of the surfactants were determined by surface tension, viscometric and spectral change methods using an anionic sensitive dye, pinacyanol chloride at the room temperature.

TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF THE COMMERCIAL GRADE SAMPLES

Composition (%)	AOS	SLS
Active content	94.1	95.2
Sodium sulphate	2.2	1.3
Sodium chloride	0.2	0.1
Free oil	1.4	1.8
Moisture	2.1	1.6

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. S. K. Suri of

Chemistry Department of I.I.T., Delhi, for chemicals and valuable suggestions.

References

1. P. H. ELWORTHY, A. T. FLORENCE and C. B. MACFARLANE, "Solubilization by Surface Active Agents", Chapman and Hall, London, 1968.
2. A. A. AL-SADEN, A. T. FLORENCE, T. L. WHATLEY, P. PUISIEUX and C. VAUTION, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1982, **86**, 51.
3. P. M. HOLLAND and D. N. RUBINGH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 1984.
4. X. Y. HUA and M. J. ROSEN, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1982, **90**, 212.
5. S. K. SURI, *Chem. Weekly*, 1989(Aug. 6), 43; *Chem. Business*, 1989 (Sept. 5), 123.
6. P. MUKERJEE and K. J. MYSELS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2937.
7. M. F. COX, N. F. BORYS and T. P. MATSON, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 1139.